

A DAMAGE MECHANICS MODEL FOR OFF-AXIS FATIGUE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES UNDER DIFFERENT STRESS RATIOS

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SUMMARY: A phenomenological model is developed for the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional polymer matrix composites subjected to constant-amplitude stress cycling with different mean stresses. Based on the non-dimensional effective stress that is interpreted as a theoretical fatigue strength ratio for cases of off-axis cyclic loading, a modified form to incorporate the effect of stress ratio over the range of non-negative mean stresses is presented. By using the modified non-dimensional effective stress, a fatigue damage mechanics model is formulated which can take into account the fiber orientation as well as mean stress dependence of the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional composites. The proposed model is characterized by a master fatigue failure surface described in terms of the normalized relation of the modified Goodman type. Through comparisons with experimental results, it is demonstrated that the off-axis S-N relationships of unidirectional carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy laminates can be adequately reproduced using the proposed fatigue model over the range of stress ratios.

KEYWORDS: polymer-matrix composites, fatigue, damage mechanics, stress ratio effect, off-axis loading, modified strength ratio, modified non-dimensional effective stress

INTRODUCTION

Under realistic service conditions, in general, most structural components made of composite laminates are subjected to complex fatigue load histories characterized by changes in the amplitude, mean, frequency and waveform of stress cycling [1]. Constituent plies of those structural laminates accordingly undergo similar variable fatigue loading. The factors that control the fatigue failure of plies can be investigated separately through simplified testing on unnotched specimens. However, understanding and modeling of the effect of mean stress on the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional composites seem to be limited due to restricted amounts of available data. El Kadi and Ellyin [2] performed off-axis fatigue tests on a unidirectional glass/epoxy laminate for various fiber orientations $\theta = 0, 19, 45, 71, 90^\circ$ under different stress ratios $R = -1, 0, 0.5$; the R -value is defined by the ratio of the minimum stress to the maximum stress in the course of fatigue loading. Their results indicate that the relative fatigue strength (i.e., the maximum fatigue stress divided by the static tensile strength) becomes lowest at $R = -1$ in the range of tested stress ratios, regardless of the fiber orientations. Similar results are obtained for the off-axis behavior of a unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminate ($\theta = 0, 10, 15, 30, 45, 90^\circ$; $R = -1, 0.1, 0.5$) [3].

As for the off-axis fatigue failure criteria that consider the effect of mean stress, we can search out the following studies. Sims and Brogdon [4] adopt the fatigue strength functions that depend on the number of cycles as well as the ratio of the alternating stress to the mean stress. Thus, this model has a capability to describe the effect of stress ratio on the off-axis fatigue behavior. El Kadi and Ellyin [2] assume the normalized strain energy changes separately for positive and negative stress ratios, respectively. These normalized measures allow us to obtain a master S-N relationship that is independent of the fiber orientation and stress ratio. Petermann and Plumtree [5] claim that the strain energy change associated with the in-plane normal and shear stresses in a critical plane becomes a unified measure to cope with the fiber orientation and stress ratio effects on the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional composites. Stress-based approaches to establishing a master S-N relationship are presented by Fawaz and Ellyin [6] and Kawai et al. [3].

The present study aims to define a unified fatigue strength measure that is useful in coping with the fiber orientation as well as mean stress dependence of the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional composites over a typical range of stress ratios. First, the conventional fatigue strength ratio, i.e. the ratio of the maximum fatigue stress to the ultimate static strength, is modified to incorporate the effect of mean stress. The modified fatigue strength ratio is applied to obtain normalized S-N relationships for the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional glass/epoxy [2] and carbon/epoxy [3] laminates. Second, a general scalar representation of the modified fatigue strength ratio is derived on the basis of the non-dimensional effective stress [7, 8]. Third, a fatigue damage mechanics model that can take into account the effect of fiber orientation and mean stress on the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional laminates is developed using the general fatigue strength measure. Finally, validity of the proposed model is evaluated on the basis of comparisons between predicted and experimental results.

NON-DIMENSIONAL FATIGUE STRENGTH MEASURE

Modified Fatigue Strength Ratio

The static strength of off-axis specimens of unidirectional composites greatly depends on the fiber orientation. To compare the off-axis fatigue strengths for different fiber orientations, therefore, some normalized strength measure should be introduced.

A simple form of the non-dimensional fatigue strength measure can be given by

$$S^* = \frac{\sigma_a}{\sigma_B - \sigma_m} \quad (1)$$

where σ_a and σ_m represent the alternating stress and the mean stress, respectively. For the case of fully reversed tension-compression fatigue loading, $R = -1$, and we can confirm that

$$S^* \Big|_{R=-1} = \frac{\sigma_{\max}}{\sigma_B} \quad (2)$$

This indicates that the non-dimensional fatigue strength measure S^* defined by equation (1) may be interpreted as a generalization of the fatigue strength ratio $s^* = \sigma_{\max} / \sigma_B$. Hence, the fatigue strength measure defined by equation (1) is called a modified fatigue strength ratio hereafter.

The fatigue strength ratio s^* becomes an effective measure for data analysis, which is confirmed early on by Basquin [9] for the fatigue behavior of metals and by Awerbuch and Hahn [10] for the off-axis fatigue response of unidirectional graphite/epoxy composites at room temperature. Recent studies [7, 8] also demonstrate that the fatigue strength ratio is useful for the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminate at room temperature as well as at high temperature.

For the fatigue behavior of metals, it is recognized by Landgraf [11] that the mean stress effect can be accounted for using the modified fatigue strength ratio S^* and it is described in terms of the linear Goodman diagram; in that fatigue data analysis, the static strength σ_B involved by the modified fatigue strength ratio is treated as a fatigue strength coefficient σ_f' that is approximated as $\sigma_f' \approx \sigma_B$. As for the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional composites, however, the validity of this form of strength measure has not been evaluated.

Comparisons With Experimental Results

For the fatigue data on a unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminate at the stress ratio $R = 0.1$ [3], two plots

Fig. 1 Off-axis S-N relationships for unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminate ($R = 0.1$)

Fig. 2 Normalized S-N relationships using the fatigue strength ratio for unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminate ($R = 0.1$)

of the maximum fatigue stress σ_{\max} and the fatigue strength ratio $s^* = \sigma_{\max} / \sigma_B$ (σ_B is treated as the static tensile strength) against the number of cycles to failure are presented in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 on logarithmic scales, respectively. In Fig. 1, we can observe that the off-axis S-N relationship plotted using σ_{\max} significantly depends on the fiber orientation θ . The normalized S-N relationship in Fig. 2 plotted using s^* demonstrates that the fatigue data points are randomly distributed in a relatively narrow band and no particular indication of the fiber orientation effect appears. This confirms that the fiber orientation dependence of the off-axis fatigue data on the unidirectional CFRP laminate for the given stress ratio can be substantially removed using the fatigue strength ratio s^* . The fatigue data for the respective fiber orientations in Fig. 1 and all data in Fig. 2 are approximately fitted by straight lines over the range of fatigue testing up to 10^6 cycles, suggesting that the S-N plots are approximately described in terms of the Basquin relation [9].

A comparison between the normalized off-axis S-N relationships for the unidirectional CFRP laminate under different stress ratios $R = 0.5, 0.1, -1$ ($\theta > 0^\circ$), $R = -0.3$ ($\theta = 0^\circ$) is shown in Fig. 3. It is clearly observed that the gradient of the straight line fitting each set of the normalized off-axis fatigue data tends to become steeper for a smaller stress ratio.

The above off-axis fatigue data for the three different stress ratios are replotted in Fig. 4 using the modified fatigue strength ratio S^* . We notice that the stress ratio dependence of the normalized off-axis fatigue data is almost removed in this normalized plot; this becomes evident, compared with the results shown in Fig. 3. The above observation indicates that the modified fatigue strength ratio S^* substantially eliminates the fiber orientation as well as mean stress dependence of the off-axis fatigue S-N relationships using the fatigue strength ratio for unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminate

Fig. 3 Effects of stress ratio on the normalized

Fig. 4 Normalized S-N relationships using a modified fatigue strength ratio for unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminate ($R = -1, -0.3, 0.1, 0.5$)

Fig. 6 Normalized S-N relationships using a modified fatigue strength ratio for unidirectional glass/epoxy laminate ($R = -1, 0, 0.5$)

Fig. 5 Effects of stress ratio on the normalized S-N relationships using the fatigue strength ratio for unidirectional glass/epoxy laminate

behavior of the unidirectional composite for a range of stress ratios, in spite of ignoring compressive stress induced effects.

For the off-axis fatigue behavior of a unidirectional glass/epoxy laminate [2] under different stress ratios $R = -1, 0, 0.5$, the normalized S-N relationships similar to the plots in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 for the unidirectional CFRP laminate are obtained, as shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. It is thus confirmed that the modified fatigue strength ratio can be used as a unified strength measure to cope with the fiber orientation as well as mean stress effect on the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional polymer matrix composites undergoing constant amplitude stress cycling in a range of stress ratios.

GENERALIZATION OF THE MODIFIED FATIGUE STRENGTH RATIO

Non-Dimensional Effective Stress

Using an arbitrary failure criterion $f(\sigma_{ij}^f) = 1$ in the stress space, we can define a non-dimensional effective stress σ^* as

$$f\left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{\sigma^*}\right) = 1 \quad (3)$$

for any state of stress σ_{ij} inside the failure surface; $\sigma^* = 1$ on the failure surface. This scalar quantity corresponds to the reciprocal of the Tsai-Hahn strength ratio [12] that indicates a quantitative measure of a safety margin for static failure.

The non-dimensional effective stress σ^* based on the Tsai-Hill static failure criterion [13] can be expressed as

$$\sigma^* = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X}\right)^2 - \frac{\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22}}{X^2} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S}\right)^2} \quad (4)$$

for the case of plane stress [7, 8], where X , Y and S are the longitudinal, transverse and shear strengths, respectively. When off-axis specimens are subjected to fatigue load in the longitudinal direction (the x direction), the non-dimensional effective stress σ_{\max}^* associated with the maximum fatigue stress σ_{\max} (> 0) can be expressed as

$$\sigma_{\max}^* = \Omega(\theta)\sigma_{\max} \quad (5)$$

where $\Omega(\theta)$ is the orientation factor given by

$$\Omega(\theta) = \sqrt{\frac{\cos^4 \theta}{X^2} - \frac{\cos^2 \theta \sin^2 \theta}{X^2} + \frac{\sin^4 \theta}{Y^2} + \frac{\sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta}{S^2}} \quad (6)$$

The maximum non-dimensional effective stress σ_{\max}^* is interpreted as a theoretical fatigue strength ratio for the case of off-axis fatigue loading. But the maximum non-dimensional effective stress σ_{\max}^* and the experimental fatigue strength ratio s^* differ in their treatment of the static strength; σ_{\max}^* is based on the predicted off-axis static strength.

Modified Non-Dimensional Effective Stress

Consider a non-dimensional scalar measure

$$\Sigma^* = \frac{\sigma_a^*}{1 - \sigma_m^*} \quad (7)$$

in the range of stress ratios $|R| \leq 1$, where σ_a^* and σ_m^* are defined as

$$\sigma_a^* = \frac{1}{2}(1 - R)\sigma_{\max}^* \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_m^* = \frac{1}{2}(1 + R)\sigma_{\max}^* \quad (9)$$

The scalar quantities σ_a^* and σ_m^* represent normalized alternating stress and normalized mean stress, respectively. Thus, the non-dimensional scalar measure Σ^* may be interpreted as a theoretical modified fatigue strength ratio for the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional composites; it is called a modified non-dimensional effective stress hereafter.

FATIGUE DAMAGE MECHANICS MODEL

Fatigue Damage Modeling

By using the modified non-dimensional effective stress, the evolution equation of the scalar fatigue damage variable ω discussed in the previous studies [7, 8] can be extended to account for the mean stress effect as

$$\frac{d\omega}{dN} = K(\Sigma^*)^{n^*} \left(\frac{1}{1-\omega} \right)^k \quad (10)$$

where K , n^* and k are material constants. This yields the following form of the fatigue life equation

(a) $R = -0.3, -1.0$

(a) $R = -1.0$

(b) $R = 0.5$

(b) $R = 0.5$

Fig. 7 On- and off-axis S-N relationships predicted using the modified fatigue model (unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminate)

Fig. 8 On- and off-axis S-N relationships predicted using the modified fatigue model (unidirectional glass/epoxy laminate)

$$N_f = \frac{1}{(\Sigma^*)^{n^*}} \quad (11)$$

Application to Off-Axis Fatigue Behavior

When $R = -1$, $\Sigma^* = \sigma_{\max}^*$. Hence, the master S-N relationship using the modified non-dimensional effective stress may be identified with the normalized S-N relationship based on the fatigue strength ratio for the case of fully reversed tension-compression cycling ($R = -1$). By a single straight-line fit

of the normalized fatigue data, the exponent n was evaluated as $n^* = 11.9$ for CFRP, and $n^* = 14.1$ for GFRP.

Comparisons between the theoretical and experimental S-N relationships at different stress ratios $R = -1$ ($\theta > 0^\circ$), -0.3 ($\theta = 0^\circ$), 0.5 are shown in Fig. 7(a) and Fig. 7(b), respectively, for the off-axis fatigue behavior of the unidirectional CFRP laminate. In view of a statistical scatter of the fatigue data, it is believed that the characteristics of the off-axis fatigue behavior can be adequately described as a whole by the fatigue damage mechanics model, regardless of the stress ratios and fiber orientations. Similar comparisons for the unidirectional GFRP laminate at different stress ratios are presented in Fig. 8(a) and Fig. 8(b). It is also seen that the effect of stress ratio on the off-axis fatigue behavior is appropriately described.

CONCLUSIONS

A non-dimensional strength measure that considers the mean stress as well as fiber orientation effects on the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional polymer matrix composites is proposed. Based on the unified fatigue measure, a damage mechanics model is then formulated. Features of the fatigue strength measure and the fatigue model are demonstrated by comparisons with experimental results. The results obtained can be summarized as follows:

- 1) A non-dimensional measure implied by the linear Goodman diagram is interpreted as a modified fatigue strength ratio S^* . Using the modified strength ratio, we can substantially remove the fiber orientation as well as stress ratio dependence of the off-axis fatigue data to obtain an experimental master S-N relationship.
- 2) A modified non-dimensional effective stress Σ^* , which is a general expression of the modified fatigue strength ratio, is defined as a natural extension of the non-dimensional effective stress σ^* based on the Tsai-Hill static failure criterion.
- 3) A fatigue damage mechanics model that considers the fiber orientation as well as stress ratio effects is formulated using the modified non-dimensional effective stress. From this model, a general fatigue life equation prescribing a normalized master S-N relationship for the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional laminates under constant amplitude stress cycling with non-negative mean stresses is derived.
- 4) The proposed fatigue model can adequately describe the off-axis S-N relationships for unidirectional glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy laminates under constant-amplitude loading with non-negative mean stresses.

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